

ISic2925

Epitaph of Martinus, a coachman

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

tabula

Editor

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Principal Contributor

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Arancio hypogeum, villa Landolina

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa

Physical Description**Dimensions**

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout**Execution**

Engraved

Letter Forms**Letter heights:**

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. † Mem[o]ria
2. Martini car
3. pentarij pa
4. triciorom

Apparatus

Text of Korhonen 2010

Manganaro: carpentari q(uondam) or carpentariq(ue)

Translation (en)

In memory of Martinus, coachman to the patricians

Commentary

Korhonen 2010: n.23 justifies reading carpentario in line 3 on the grounds that such a mixture of cases is attested in other examples.

Digital identifiers:

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EDR 073822
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